

Deliverable D4.3 Review of effectiveness of the Node Impact Assessment Toolkit

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Log of changes

DATE	Mvm	Who	Description
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07/07/2023	0v1	Corinne Martin (ELIXIR Hub)	Initial version
17/07/2023	0v2	Corinne Martin (ELIXIR Hub)	Sent to PMU after incorporating internal WP feedback
11/07/2023	0v3	Nikki Coutts (ELIXIR Hub)	Circulated to the MB for final review before submission
18/07/2023	0v4	Corinne Martin (ELIXIR Hub)	MB comments addressed
20/07/2023	1v0	Nikki Coutts (ELIXIR Hub)	Final version to be uploaded into EC Portal

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1. Executive Summary

An Impact Toolkit was created to support performance and impact evaluation in ELIXIR. The intended audience of this Toolkit is operators, developers and managers wishing to demonstrate and communicate the performance, impact, and ultimately public value of their research infrastructure, to their particular set of funders and stakeholders. The Impact Toolkit collates a range of impact-related materials including training materials, worked examples, factsheets, lists of indicators, key publication, case studies, and presentation slides. These materials were created and/or brought together using a bottom-up approach that tried to reflect the varied needs of Nodes in ELIXIR member countries. The main **outcome** from this work is an increased capacity at Node level to

demonstrate and communicate public value to funders and other key stakeholders, thereby contributing to long-term sustainability of Node-led activities.

2. Contribution toward project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

Objective no. / Key Result no. Description	Contributed to:
Objective 1: Develop a sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support by leveraging national capabilities (WP1, WP5)	
Key Result 1.1: Established European expert network of data stewards that connect national data centres and similar infrastructures and drive the development of interoperable solutions following international best practice, including national interpretations of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	No
Key Result 1.2: Development of joint guidelines and common toolkit that are adopted into funder recommendations, with support available nationally and in local languages	No
Key Result 1.3: The catalogue of successful national business models incorporated into national strategies	No
Key Result 1.4: The developed “sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support” is adopted into national ELIXIR Node	No
Objective 2: Strengthen Europe’s data management capacity through a comprehensive training programme delivered throughout the European Research Area (WP2, WP6)	
Key Result 2.1: A comprehensive ELIXIR Training and Capacity building programme in Data Management, directed at both data managers and ELIXIR users, and connected to the national training programmes in Data Management in the ELIXIR Nodes and prospective ELIXIR Member countries.	No
Key Result 2.2: Development of a collective group of trainers that support scalable deployment of Data Management training across ELIXIR Nodes.	No
Key Result 2.3: A substantial cohort of data managers, Node coordinators and researchers with specific data management skills, business planning and knowledge of transnational operations across the ELIXIR Nodes	No
Objective 3: Align national data management standards and services through a sustainable,	

scalable and cost-effective data management toolkit (WP2, WP3, WP5)	
Key Result 3.1: Assemble a full-stack harmonised common toolkit comprising all aspects of data management: from data capture, annotation, and sharing; to integration with analysis platforms and making the data publicly available according to international standards.	No
Key Result 3.2: Provide exemplar toolkit configurations for prioritised demonstrators to serve as templates for future use.	No
Key Result 3.3: Establish national capacity in using as well as updating, extending and sustaining the toolkit across the ERA.	No
Key Result 3.4: Enable 'FAIR at source' practice for data generation, and analytical process pipeline implementation by flexible deployment of the toolkit in national operations	No
Objective 4: Align national investments to drive local impact and global influence of ELIXIR (WP4,WP6)	
Key Result 4.1: Development of a Node Impact Assessment Toolkit based on RI-PATHS methodology.	Yes
Key Result 4.2: Adoption of Impact assessment in ELIXIR Nodes, supported by Node coordinators network and feedback on applicability from dialogues with national funders.	Yes
Key Result 4.3: Creation of national public-private partnerships and industry outreach where open life-science data and services stimulate local bioeconomy	No
Key Result 4.4: Growth in reach, impact and engagement of stakeholder communication assessed by established ELIXIR Communications metrics	No
Key Result 4.5: Initiating and advancing discussions on Membership (EU and international) or strategic partnerships (international countries) following ELIXIR-CONVERGE workshops.	No

3. Introduction

Demonstrating the scientific and socio-economic impacts of ELIXIR, a pan-European research infrastructure with a global user base, is central to ensuring its long-term sustainability, and hence its capacity to support users of its services in replying to scientific, industrial and societal challenges. In line with this ambition, an Impact Toolkit was created to support performance and impact evaluation in ELIXIR. The intended audience of this Toolkit is operators, developers and managers wishing to demonstrate and communicate the performance, impact, and ultimately public value of their research infrastructure, to their particular set of funders and stakeholders.

4. Description of work accomplished

The Impact Toolkit collates a range of impact-related materials including training materials, worked examples, factsheets, lists of indicators, key published references, case studies, and slides. These materials were created and/or brought together using a bottom-up approach that tried to reflect the varied needs of Nodes in ELIXIR member countries.

The bulk of the work to arrive at this Toolkit was funded through Task 4.4 of ELIXIR-CONVERGE, together with a Strategic Implementation Study¹ funded by ELIXIR's own (core) funding (EUR 168,562). Pooling resources allowed ELIXIR to involve a total of 17 Nodes in this collective effort, some funded through ELIXIR-CONVERGE, others through the Strategic Implementation Study, and yet other Nodes chose to engage in-kind as they saw value in being involved.

The approach leading to the Toolkit was three-fold:

1. Nodes took part in specialised **training events**², facilitated by impact experts (EFIS Centre),
2. Nodes then undertook **case studies**³, which they chose, based on their needs, as influenced by their national circumstances and particular sets of stakeholders. They had the opportunity to be mentored through:
 - ad-hoc and informal requests for support and advice, or
 - more formal "support calls" where Nodes came with specific questions to ask to the experts, whom in turn provided dedicated feedback based on materials submitted ahead of the call,
3. Nodes took part in a series of "Show and Tell" **knowledge-exchange events** [see list in section "6. Impact case studies" of the Toolkit, Annex 1] in which Nodes presented their chosen case studies, for peer feedback. In total, 14 case studies were presented as part of 11 events, each with approximately 15-20 attendees.

5. Results

The main **output** from this work is ELIXIR's Impact Toolkit, an advanced draft of which is provided in Annex 1. At the time of writing this deliverable (July 2023), the document is out for review by its contributors, and will be published on ELIXIR's Gateway in F1000Research⁴ early September 2023. Contributors will then be able to link it to their ORCID by using the DOI provided.

A range of **dissemination** measures was employed throughout the duration of ELIXIR-CONVERGE, so that lessons-learned and associated good practices benefit more widely across ELIXIR, and beyond. They included:

¹ <https://elixir-europe.org/internal-projects/commissioned-services/impact-evaluation>

² <https://elixir-europe.org/events/getting-started-impact-evaluation> ;
<https://elixir-europe.org/events/converge-workshop-series-repeat-event-getting-started-impact-evaluation>

³ A case study is an activity or set of activities, carried out or planned by a Node, and whose impact will be evaluated during the project.

⁴ <https://f1000research.com/gateways/elixir?selectedDomain=documents>

- a public-facing project **webpage**⁵ providing background to the work as well as links to outputs,
- four ELIXIR **news items**:
 - “*Building capacity in impact evaluation at ELIXIR*”⁶ (August 2022, >2,600 views at the time of writing),
 - “*Measuring the impact of ELIXIR’s training*”⁷ (January 2023, >1,240 views at the time of writing)
 - “*Highlights of ELIXIR-supported publications in 2022*”⁸ (relating to one of the case studies) (March 2023, >800 views at the time of writing),
 - “*ELIXIR’s role in shaping policy*”⁹ (July 2023, >240 views at the time of writing).
- a **mini-Symposium** at the ELIXIR All Hands (June 2023, >40 attendees) entitled “*In conversation with...*” - *ELIXIR’s impact at Node-level*¹⁰, during which four Nodes shared:
 - the new skills that they had developed (or strengthened),
 - the new systems they had put in place (or improved) to document their impact,
 - how they had used the evidence of impact,
 - plus any lesson learned along that journey,
- four **publications** acknowledging support from ELIXIR-CONVERGE (metrics are at the time of writing):
 - “*Demonstrating public value to funders and other stakeholders—the journey of ELIXIR*”¹¹ (May 2021, 6 citations) in *Annals of Public and Cooperative Economics*,
 - “*Measuring outcomes and impact from the BioHackathon Europe*”¹² (August 2021, >770 views, >270 downloads) in *BioHackrXiv Preprints*,
 - “*Making European performance and impact assessment frameworks for research infrastructures glocal*”¹³ (March 2022, >1,100 views, >100 downloads) in *F1000Research*, with related *Blog*¹⁴,
 - “*The road to success: drawing parallels between 'road' and 'research data' infrastructures to foster understanding between service providers, funders and policymakers*”¹⁵ (January 2023, >530 views, >30 downloads),
- provision of content for ELIXIR’s Impact Dashboard¹⁶ (>8,000 views at the time of writing), and
- a range of presentations and posters at various events (tracked at project-level).

⁵ <https://elixir-europe.org/internal-projects/commissioned-services/impact-evaluation>

⁶ <https://elixir-europe.org/news/impact>

⁷ <https://elixir-europe.org/news/training-metrics-db>

⁸ <https://elixir-europe.org/news/publications-2022>

⁹ <https://elixir-europe.org/news/policy-impact>

¹⁰ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1tUDd_vwqqGLOJsqjQpGYmwGTPcn6l5uUxMh5aMB_-8/edit

¹¹ <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/apce.12328>

¹² <https://biohackrxiv.org/3dxhg/>

¹³ <https://f1000research.com/articles/11-278>

¹⁴ <https://blog.f1000.com/2022/11/24/global-frameworks-local-research-infrastructures/>

¹⁵ <https://f1000research.com/articles/12-88>

¹⁶ <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/impact>

6. Conclusions

The main **outcome** from this work is an increased capacity at Node level to demonstrate and communicate public value to funders and other key stakeholders, thereby contributing to long-term sustainability of Node-led activities. This aligns directly with one of the 2020 recommendations of a High-Level Expert Group which assessed the progress of ESFRI¹⁷ and other world class research infrastructures towards implementation and long-term sustainability¹⁸. This work has reinforced the ‘community of practice’ that was emerging, across ELIXIR, around impact evaluation.

7. Impact

ELIXIR’s work on impact, notably in the context of distributed life sciences RIs, much of which has been supported by ELIXIR-CONVERGE, is increasingly recognised and appreciated externally. For instance:

- invitation to share experience at an EOSC-life knowledge-sharing workshop¹⁹ (March 2023) convened by EATRIS, a sibling research infrastructure in the life sciences,
- mentions in a policy brief²⁰ (May 2023) by the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) entitled “*Impact assessment of RIs*”,
- mentions in a report²¹ (July 2023) by the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) entitled “*Very Large Research Infrastructures Policy issues and options*”,
- guest lecturer at the RItrainplus course²² (July 2023) on the socio-economic impact of research infrastructures,
- guest trainer at EMBL-EBI’s course²³ (November 2023) on Managing a bioinformatics core facility.

8. Next Steps

Once published, the Toolkit will be disseminated through a range of measures:

- ELIXIR’s usual communications channels (Weekly Brief reaching 800 recipients across the ELIXIR membership, social media),
- an invited ELIXIR webinar²⁴ (September 2023),
- a dedicated slide in ELIXIR’s standard slide deck,

¹⁷ European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures

¹⁸

https://ec.europa.eu/info/publications/supporting-transformative-impact-research-infrastructures-european-research_en

¹⁹

<https://eatris.eu/news/eatris-publishes-workshop-report-on-impact-assessment-of-research-infrastructures/>

²⁰ https://www.esfri.eu/sites/default/files/ESFRI_Impact_Policy_Brief_23052023.pdf

²¹ https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/fr/science-and-technology/very-large-research-infrastructures_2b93187f-en

²² <https://ritrainplus.eu/2023/01/13/socio-economic-impact-of-ris/>

²³ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/training/events/managing-bioinformatics-core-facility-2/>

²⁴ <https://elixir-europe.org/events-type/webinars>

- mentions in various internal ELIXIR documents and guidelines, such as templates for internal project proposals, ELIXIR's Handbook of Operations²⁵, the curriculum of ELIXIR's Training Programme in Management (ELITMa),
- mentions on various impact-related web pages, e.g.
 - landing page²⁶ of ELIXIR's Impact Focus Group (public-facing, it has had >11,000 views since its creation in 2019),
 - project webpage²⁷ (public-facing) and its sibling page as part of the ELIXIR-CONVERGE area²⁸,
 - mention in a relevant page²⁹ of ELIXIR's impact dashboard.

It is hoped that the Toolkit will also be referenced in various external curricula for the development of managers of research infrastructures (e.g. Rltrainplus course on the socio-economic impact of research infrastructures³⁰, the Executive Masters in Management of Research Infrastructures³¹).

It is anticipated that the Toolkit will be maintained as a 'living document' on the ELIXIR Intranet³², with periodic public-facing updates released on F1000Research. Many of these updates will likely be produced as part of an ELIXIR-funded project under the upcoming 2024-2028 ELIXIR Scientific Programme.

9. Deviation from Description of Action

N/A

²⁵ <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/governance/handbook-operations>

²⁶ <https://elixir-europe.org/focus-groups/impact>

²⁷ <https://elixir-europe.org/internal-projects/commissioned-services/impact-evaluation>

²⁸ <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/how-funded/eu-projects/converge/wp4>

²⁹ <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/impact/more-examples>

³⁰ <https://ritrainplus.eu/2023/01/13/socio-economic-impact-of-ris/>

³¹ <http://ritrain.eu/executive-masters>

³² <https://elixir-europe.org/documents/elixirs-impact-toolkit>

Annex 1. ELIXIR's Impact Toolkit

